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Top Cited Papers

AN IMPLEMENTATION OF INTRUSION DETECTION SYSTEM USING GENETIC ALGORITHM

Md. Abdul Mukit² and Md. Abu Naser Bikas³ Mohammad Sazzadul Hoque¹

Cited by 265

ABSTRACT

❖ Nowadays it is very important to maintain a high level security to ensure safe and trusted communication of information between various organizations. But secured data communication over internet and any other network is always under threat of intrusions and misuses. So Intrusion Detection Systems have become a needful component in terms of computer and network security.

❖ This approach uses evolution theory to information evolution in order to filter the traffic data and thus reduce the complexity. To implement and measure the performance of our system we used the KDD99 benchmark dataset and obtained reasonable detection rate.

KEYWORDS

Computer & Network Security, Intrusion Detection, Intrusion Detection System, Genetic Algorithm, KDD Cup 1999 Dataset.

Paper Link

<http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0312nsa08.pdf>

AIRCC Publication

AN OVERVIEW OF THE SECURITY CONCERNS IN ENTERPRISE CLOUD COMPUTING

Anthony Bisong and Syed (Shawon) M. Rahman

Cited by 222

ABSTRACT

- ❖ Deploying cloud computing in an enterprise infrastructure bring significant security concerns. Successful implementation of cloud computing in an enterprise requires proper planning and understanding of emerging risks, threats, vulnerabilities, and possible countermeasures.
- ❖ We believe enterprise should analyze the company/organization security risks, threats, and available countermeasures before adopting this technology. In this paper, we have discussed security risks and concerns in cloud computing and enlightened steps that an enterprise can take to reduce security risks and protect their resources.
- ❖ We have also explained cloud computing strengths/benefits, weaknesses, and applicable areas in information risk management.

Paper Link

<http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0111jnsa03.pdf>

AIRCC Publication

USING ROUGH SET AND SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE FOR NETWORK INTRUSION DETECTION

Kai-Fan Cheng and Chia-Fen Hsieh Rung-Ching Chen

ABSTRACT

Cited by 138

- ❖ The main function of IDS (Intrusion Detection System) is to protect the system, analyze and predict the behaviors of users. Then these behaviors will be considered an attack or a normal behavior.
- ❖ Though IDS has been developed for many years, the large number of return alert messages makes managers maintain system inefficiently. In this paper, we use RST (Rough Set Theory) and SVM (Support Vector Machine) to detect intrusions. First, RST is used to preprocess the data and reduce the dimensions.
- ❖ Next, the features were selected by RST will be sent to SVM model to learn and test respectively. The method is effective to decrease the space density of data. The experiments will compare the results with different methods and show RST and SVM schema could improve the false positive rate and accuracy.

KEYWORDS

Rough Set; Support Vector Machine; Intrusion Detection System; Attack Detection Rate;

Paper Link

<http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0409s1.pdf>

AIRCC Publication

COMBINING NAIVE BAYES AND DECISION TREE FOR ADAPTIVE INTRUSION DETECTION

Mohammad Zahidur Rahman Dewan Md. Farid, Nouria Harbi

Cited by 135

ABSTRACT

❖The proposed algorithm also addresses some difficulties of data mining such as handling continuous attribute, dealing with missing attribute values, and reducing noise in training data. Due to the large volumes of security audit data as well as the complex and dynamic properties of intrusion behaviours, several data mining based intrusion detection techniques have been applied to network-based traffic data and host-based data in the last decades

❖The experimental results prove that the proposed algorithm achieved high detection rates (DR) and significant reduce false positives (FP) for different types of network intrusions using limited computational resources.

KEYWORDS

Decision Tree, Detection Rate, False Positive, Naive Bayesian classifier, Network Intrusion Detection

Paper Link

<http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0410ijnsa2.pdf>

AIRCC Publication

SECURITY CHALLENGES, ISSUES AND THEIR SOLUTIONS FOR VANET

Ram Shringar Raw , Manish Kumar and Nanhay Singh

Cited by 132

ABSTRACT

❖ Vehicular Ad hoc Networks (VANETs) are the promising approach to provide safety and other applications to the drivers as well as passengers. It becomes a key component of the intelligent transport system. A lot of works have been done towards it but security in VANET got less attention

❖ In this article, we have discussed about the VANET and its technical and security challenges. We have also discussed some major attacks and solutions that can be implemented against these attacks.

KEYWORDS

VANET, VANET architecture, ARAN, SEAD, SMT, NDM, ARIADNE

Paper Link

<http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/5513nsa08.pdf>

AIRCC Publication

CLOUD COMPUTING AND SECURITY ISSUES IN THE CLOUD

Monjur Ahmed¹ and Mohammad Ashraf Hossain²

Cited by 122

ABSTRACT

❖ Cloud computing has formed the conceptual and infrastructural basis for tomorrow's computing. The global computing infrastructure is rapidly moving towards cloud based architecture. While it is important to take advantages of cloud based computing by means of deploying it in diversified sectors, the security aspects in a cloud based computing environment remains at the core of interest.

❖ If security is not robust and consistent, the flexibility and advantages that cloud computing has to offer will have little credibility. This paper presents a review on the cloud computing concepts as well as security issues inherent within the context of cloud computing and cloud infrastructure.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, cloud service, cloud security, computer network, distributed computing, security.

Paper Link

<http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/6114nsa03.pdf>

AIRCC Publication

ANALYSIS OF WEB LOGS AND WEB USER IN WEB MINING

Dhinaharan Nagamalai, L.K. Joshila Grace, V.Maheswari

Cited by 118

ABSTRACT

❖ Log files contain information about User Name, IP Address, Time Stamp, Access Request, number of Bytes Transferred, Result Status, URL that Referred and User Agent. The log files are maintained by the web servers.

❖ By analysing these log files gives a neat idea about the user. This paper gives a detailed discussion about these log files, their formats, their creation, access procedures, their uses, various algorithms used and the additional arameters that can be used in the log files which in turn gives way toan effective mining. It also provides the idea of creating an extended log file and learning the user behaviour.

KEYWORDS

Web Log file, Web usage mining, Web servers, Log data, Log Level directive.

Paper Link

<http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/0111jnsa07.pdf>

AIRCC Publication

SECURITY ISSUES ASSOCIATED WITH BIG DATA IN CLOUD COMPUTING

Venkata Narasimha Inukollu¹ , Sailaja Arsi¹ and Srinivasa Rao Ravuri³

Cited by 109

ABSTRACT

❖ In this paper, we discuss security issues for cloud computing, Big data, Map Reduce and Hadoop environment. The main focus is on security issues in cloud computing that are associated with big data.

❖ Big data applications are a great benefit to organizations, business, companies and many large scale and small scale industries. We also discuss various possible solutions for the issues in cloud computing security and Hadoop.

❖ cloud computing, big data and its applications, advantages are likely to represent the most promising new frontiers in science.

KEYWORDS

Cloud Computing, Big Data, Hadoop, Map Reduce, HDFS (Hadoop Distributed File System)

Paper Link

<http://airccse.org/journal/nsa/6314nsa04.pdf>

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- ❖ Intrusion Detection and Prevention
- ❖ Internet Security & Applications
- ❖ Security & Network Management
- ❖ E-mail security, Spam, Phishing, E-mail fraud
- ❖ Virus, worms, Trojan Protection
- ❖ Security threats & countermeasures (DDoS, MiM, Session Hijacking, Replay attack etc.)
- ❖ Ubiquitous Computing Security
- ❖ Web 2.0 security
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